

Tunisian Women's Associations

By Tatiana Hernández-Justo, University of Granada, Spain

Entry tags: Religious Group, Islamic Traditions, Sunni

Although not a conventional religious group per se, Tunisian Women's Associations during colonial times had ties and strong relationships with the religious establishments. In this entry we will cover the biggest and most important, native ones: l'Union Musulmane des Femmes Tunisiennes (UMFT) and l'Union des Filles Tunisiennes (UFT).

Date Range: 1936 CE - 1962 CE

Region: Tunisia

Region tags: Africa, Northern Africa, Tunisia

Tunisia

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Šāms al-islām (شمس الإسلام)
- Source 2: Tūnis al-fatāt (تونس الفتاة)
- Source 3: Femmes de Tunisie and Jeunes Femmes de Tunisie

Notes: All of these were journals or periodicals. The first one, founded by Bachira Ben Murad's father, was religious at its core, but regularly incorporated articles about female education, women's rights in the Qur'an, etc. The second was the print media of the UMFT, whereas the last couple of them pertained to the Union des Femmes de Tunisie and the Union des Jeunes Filles de Tunisie (UJFT) respectively, both of them women's associations linked to the Communist Party.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <http://chnm.gmu.edu/wwh/p/184.html>
- Source 1 Description: An interview carried out in 1998 by Julia A. Clancy Smith to Tawhida ben al-Shaykh, available at the Center for History and New Media in Women in World History.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bpt6k6204389q/f20.image.texteImage>
- Source 1 Description: Digitized version of ESSNOUSSI, Mohammed (1897): Épanouissement de la fleur ou étude sur la femme dans l'islam, Tunis, Imprimerie Rapide, 1897.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: The conservative shuyukh of al-Zaytuna were very much enemies to these organizations and competed against them to capture the masses' attention. They also sought to discredit and undermine women's associations.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– No

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Notes: Some of the reformist shuyukh did not pose a threat to the women's associations. A number of them even publicly sided with said associations.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– I don't know

Notes: There are no records of specifically violent reactions towards the women involved in the associations. However, many of them suffered public scorn from the conservative milieu and some of them were ostracized for joining the associations, so some sort of conflict was indeed present at the time. However, the worst conflict often went to people who worked more openly on women's rights, particularly those coming from a secular background, such as individual scholars like Tahar Haddad. It is true, though, that the associations linked to the communist party had a worst social perception from Tunisian people as they were seen as imposing a European agenda in the country.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– I don't know

Notes: All of the women who joined the UMFT were not only Muslim, but almost always of the maliki school. The same is true for the UFT, whereas women who joined the UFT or the UJFT were non-Muslim.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

Notes: All women's associations tried their best to expand their numbers by disseminating their ideas through the written press as well as in-person meetings and actions. However, they were not proselytizing their religion, but their ideology.

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– I don't know

Notes: There was no official support, but the nationalist party did somewhat side with the UMFT and the UFT and members of both of them, namely Bachira ben Murad, regularly attended the party's demonstrations and political rallies.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– I don't know

Notes: There was in the sense of being Muslims and in adhering to the nationalist cause for the UMFT and UFT, but not in a regulated sense.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– I don't know

Notes: There seem to be no written records that specify the number of women who had joined either of the Muslim associations at hand, but Hassine Raouf Hamza estimates that the number of women who

were active members of the Tunisian Communist Party as well as either one of their female associations were about 500.

Reference: Hassine Hamza Raouf. *Communisme et nationalisme en Tunisie. De la Libération à l'indépendance*. Tunis: Éditions de l'Université de Tunis I.

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (not related to larger religious group)

Notes: Although the UMFT and the UFT had no direct links to other religious groups and were primarily a nationalist group, they had ideological ties to the Islamic reformist movement. As for the communist associations, they did have a clear relationship to the Communist Party.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– I don't know

Notes: The exact role that Bachira ben Murad played in the UMFT is not hierarchical per se for there are no records of her ever trying to maintain a position of power amongs fellow colleagues. However, she was the spearhead of the association and, as such, she had a clear say in what was to be done and what wasn't.

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– No

Notes: Founders of each association were automatically considered its leaders and there is nothing that could suggest a democratic voting process to select one, even in the communist associations.

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– I don't know

Notes: Examples of problems between participants and leaders seem to be slightly more prominent in the communist associations, although they are scarce even there. However, it was possible for a member of the association to raise a claim against the leaders if they thought the leaders weren't making the correct choices. How such a claim would be solved is unclear.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:
– I don't know

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:
– Yes

Notes: Religious and political rulers with enmity towards either of the associations would take each chance they had to criticize its leaders, but it often had no effect on the association's inner hierarchy at all.

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:
– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: In a sense, the UMFT and the UFT, as Muslim women's associations, did follow the general religious scriptures of Islam, but they cannot be considered as "scriptures" pertaining to this group. The same is true for the rules and inner regulations of the Communist Party for those associations. However, each association had their written press media which could be understood as being a collection of authoritative texts.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: However, most UMFT and UFT women did attend every single nationalist event there was, even political rallies and demonstrations.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: However, since these associations were all founded after the enforcement Law of Naturalization of 1924, they did not engage in the controversies relating whether the bodies of formerly Tunisian people who had been granted French nationality could or could not be buried in Islamic cemeteries.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

Notes: Although Allah is described with anthropomorphic vocabulary, Allah is not anthropomorphic.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
 - No
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - I don't know
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample

region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - No
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - No
 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - No
 - ↳ Through divination practices:
 - No
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - I don't know
 - Notes: Technically, God can communicate with the living directly. However, most often than not it is done only through prophets.
 - ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
 - ↳ Other form of communication with living:
 - I don't know

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Despite the belief in angels (ملائكة) and junun (جنون) being present in Islam, hence in the members of the Muslim associations, it was irrelevant to their goals and means.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Angels do.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Junun (جنون) do.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

- ↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:
Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
 - Yes

- ↳ Adultery:
 - Yes

- ↳ Incest:
 - Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Any sexual orientation other than heterosexuality is forbidden.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:
– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
– I don't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:
– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:
– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]
– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:
– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
– Yes

- ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done randomly:
 - No
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - No
 - Notes: Muslim women's associations abided by the general, hegemonic rules of Sunni (maliki) Islam, but they did not emphasize issues that had little or no relation to women's rights.
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - No
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:
 - No
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:
 - No
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness[]:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– I don't know

- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
 - No
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
 - I don't know

Notes: None of this seemed particularly important for the members of the associations at hand, since it usually had little to do with their goals.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Notes: For the Muslim associations, there was the belief that by fighting for the betterment of the country and its independence and continuing the struggle for the betterment of women's lives, there would be a new social order. The same is also true for the communist associations, despite the nuances being completely different.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The Muslim groups rooted all of their social norms in the Qur'an or the ahadith. However, they employed modernist and reformist readings as the base for their ideology, so there were certain ideas that were not shared by the hegemonic interpretation of Islam at the time, such as the education of women. The communist groups believed that most of the hegemonic social norms of the time were either outdated or directly based on classist, racist and capitalist ideals and, as such, said groups strove to change them.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present and clear

Notes: Particularly amongst the Muslim association and considering how they supported reformist ideas, there was a clear distinction between which social or religious rules could and should be changed and which of them couldn't. The same is not so true for the communist associations.

Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– No

Notes: However, Muslim groups advocated the elimination of the integral veil, which can be viewed as a specifically moral norm not prescribed, but encouraged by the associations.

Moral norms apply to:

– Only one gender

– All individuals within society

Notes: Some of the norms they were trying to change and/or enforce were aimed specifically towards women, as is to be expected coming from a women's association. Others, such as to respect every person regardless of their gender or social class, applied to society as a whole. The communist groups had a more clear emphasis on the idea that no difference should be made between moral norms applicable to women and men as both genders were an equal part of society. In spite of this, they still run a women's-only periodical and none of their meetings could be attended by men.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

Courage (in battle):

– Yes

Notes: Considering the term "battle" as a struggle against either European colonialism (in the case of Muslim associations) or capitalism, both types of associations placed great emphasis in the need for their members to be courageous.

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

Notes: Only applies to Muslim associations.

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

Notes: Only applies to Muslim associations.

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

Notes: Both Muslim and communist associations encouraged their members to contribute to social justice causes such as the funding schools, helping the poor or supporting comrades in strikes (this last one only applies to communist associations).

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

Notes: Only applies to Muslim associations.

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

Notes: Only applies to Muslim associations.

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Yes

Notes: Only applies to communist associations.

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– I don't know

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

Notes: Only applies to Muslim associations.

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– I don't know

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– I don't know

↳ Strength (physical):

– No

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– No

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

Notes: Only applies to Muslim associations.

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

Notes: Only applies to Muslim associations.

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– No

↳ Optimism / hope:

– No

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

Notes: Only applies to Muslim associations.

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

Notes: Only applies to Muslim associations.

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– No

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

Notes: Both types of associations strove to provide good education to women and placed great importance in it.

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– No

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Both groups required its members to attend regular meetings as well as participate in the activities each of them promoted, be it strikes, political rallies, demonstrations, crowdsourcing events, etc.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: Although it was not a requirement, marginalization by out-group members (particularly those coming from a conservative background) was often a side effect of being part of one of these associations.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: At the very least, both the Muslim and the communist associations strove to provide for the needy and poor, be it on the grounds of religious precepts for the former or on camaraderie for the latter. The extent to which this would have been feasible given the situation is unproved as of yet, but neither ones nor the others had large funding available.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: See previous note.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: In the case of Muslim adherents, there was supposed to be a certain degree of poverty relief based on the regular zakat collected by mosques; however this only happened in theory and not in practice.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: Neither groups had the resources to provide formal education to its adherents, but both Muslim and communist associations advocated for education amongst women. As such, many of them participated in a crowdfunding by the feminine wing of the Association of Young Muslims (Ittiḥād al-Ašbāb al-Muṣlīmīn) which resulted in the establishment of a new school for Muslim girls in 1944.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: Clarifications should be made as to whether Muslim Tunisian women really did have access to education. There were few schools for girls in the country and even fewer higher education options. It is not as if they were legally barred from receiving an education, but there were few options (most of them, French schools) and society strongly opposed their education. As such, Muslim women did have access to education, but it was not easy, therefore many didn't get one.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: In the case of the communist groups, they interacted regularly with their party's bureaucracies.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Élise Abassade. L'Union des femmes de Tunisie et l'Union des jeunes filles de Tunisie, 1944-1957. Deux associations féminines et communistes?. doi: 10.3917/mond1.152.0197.

Reference: Élise Abassade. Un "peuple" au féminin? Étude de deux journaux féminins communistes de Tunisie (1945-1946).

Reference: Souad Bakalti. La femme tunisienne au temps de la colonisation (1881-1956). Paris: L'Harmattan.

Reference: Sophie Bessis , Souhayr Belhassen. Femmes du Maghreb : l'enjeu. Paris: Lattès.

Reference: Sophie Bessis. Le féminisme institutionnel en Tunisie.

Reference: Saida Chaouachi. Le statut juridique de la femme en Tunisie. (Aïcha Belarbi), Droits de citoyenneté des femmes au Maghreb. Casablanca: Le Fennec.

Reference: Mounira Charrad. States and Women's Rights: The Making of Postcolonial Tunisia. Algeria, Morocco and California: California University Press.

Reference: Julia Clancy-Smith. L'école Rue du Pacha, Tunis: l'enseignement de la femme arabe et 'la Plus Grande France' (1900-1914).

Reference: Hassine Hamza Raouf. Communisme et nationalisme en Tunisie. De la Libération à l'indépendance. Tunis: Éditions de l'Université de Tunis I.

Reference: Amel Mahfoudh , Dorra Mahfoudh. Mobilisations des femmes et mouvement féministe en Tunisie. doi: 10.3917/nqf.332.0014.

Reference: Ilhem Marzouki. Le mouvement des femmes en Tunisie au XXème siècle. Paris: Maisonneuve et Larose.

Reference: Emma Murphy C.. Women in Tunisia: between state feminism and economic reform. (Eleanor Abdella Doumato , Maya Pripstein Posusney), Women and globalization in the Arab Middle East. Colorado

and London: Lynne Rienner.

Reference: Carmelo Pérez-Beltrán. Panorámica sobre el status social de la mujer magrebí.

Reference: Al-Hayzan Za'afan. Zuhur al-harakat al-niswiyya fi-l-`alam al-'arabi wa-mašru' tahrir al-mar'a.

Reference: T. Hernández-Justo. Between individual thinkers and women's associations: an overview of the "female issue" during the first half of the French protectorate in Tunisia. doi: <https://doi.org/10.15366/reim2022.32.002>.

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Hassine Hamza Raouf. Communisme et nationalisme en Tunisie. De la Libération à l'indépendance. Tunis: Éditions de l'Université de Tunis I.